

AMADEUS

ultra high temperature energy storage

**NEXT GENERATION MATERIALS AND SOLID STATE DEVICES FOR
ULTRA HIGH TEMPERATURE ENERGY STORAGE AND CONVERSION**

The AMADEUS Project is funded by the European Union's Horizon2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement 737054.

AMADEUS Main Results

- The proof of concept of an ultra high temperature latent heat storage device with integrated solid state energy conversion.
- The proof of concept of a new hybrid thermionic-photovoltaic energy converter.
- Fe-Si-B alloys with latent heats in the range of 3.0 - 4.8 kJ/cm³ (830 - 1320 kWh/m³), melting temperature of ~ 1220 °C.
- Cr-Si-B alloys with latent heats in the range of 4.8 - 5.1 kJ/cm³ (1320 - 1420 kWh/m³), and melting temperature of ~ 1430 °C.
- Large area lanthanum boride thin-films (> 100 nm) with work function of 2.6 eV.
- Large area barium fluoride ultra-thin films (~ 1 nm) with work function of 2.1 eV.
- New tools and procedures for:
 - Developing dielectric micro- (< 10 μm) and macro- (> 10 μm) spacers.
 - Measuring the latent heat of silicon alloys using h-BN containers and spray coatings.
 - Examining the interaction of liquid silicon alloys with refractory materials at temperatures up to 1750 °C.
 - Fabricating silicon alloys using h-BN capillaries and containers.
 - Measuring thermal conductivity in different gas atmospheres.
 - Epitaxial growth of InGaAs semiconductors on InP substrates.
 - Measuring the conversion efficiency of thermophotovoltaic devices.
 - Simulating heat transfer and phase change phenomena in the whole storage system.
 - Simulating the integration of power-to-heat-to-power storage devices in buildings.

All the project publications and data are accessible in Open-Access at AMADEUS community in www.zenodo.org/communities/

AMADEUS Expected Impacts

- Positioning this new technology in the future roadmaps of energy storage.
- Enabling a new generation of concentrated solar power systems.
- Enabling new systems for heat storage and power generation in buildings.
- New devices for waste heat recovery in high temperature industries.
- Enabling future devices for energy storage in space applications

AMADEUS Scope

AMADEUS project has developed new materials and devices that enable the storage and conversion of energy at extremely high temperatures (>1000°C), well beyond the current technological limits. Using these new components, a new kind of latent heat thermal energy storage device with unprecedented high energy density potential has been built. AMADEUS is the first project of this kind that aims at kick-starting an emerging research community around this new technological option.

Krakow

Trondheim

Rome

Madrid

Stuttgart

Athens

AMADEUS Project Concept

Project Consortium

IES-UPM:
Institute for Solar Energy - Technical University of Madrid (Spain)

CERTH-CPERI:
Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - Chemical Process Engineering Research Institute (Greece)

FRI:
Centre for High Temperature Studies, Foundry Research Institute (Poland)

NTNU:
Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Department of Materials Science and Engineering (Norway)

CNR-ISM:
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche - Institute of Structure of Matter (Italy)

USTUTT:
Institute of Building Energetics, Thermotechnology and Energy Storage (IGTE) of the University of Stuttgart (Germany)

IONVAC:
Ionvac Process Srl. (Italy)

AMADEUS Coordinator

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Project Details

Duration: 36 months

Start date: 01-01-2017

End date: 31-12-2019

Budget: 3,270,496.25 €

For more information

www.amadeus-project.eu

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